

In the IR, it absorbs at $\nu_{\max}$ 1722, 1592, 821 cm^{-1} (coumarin). The NMR spectrum was taken in CDCl_3 solution with TMS as the internal reference. It showed peaks at δ (in p.p.m) 1.66, 1.74 (C-methyls), 4.18 (s, methoxy), 4.80 (d, $J=7$ Hz, α -methylene), 5.42 (t, $J=7$ Hz, vinyl), 6.28 (d, $J=10$ Hz, H-3), 6.98 (d, $J=2$ Hz, H-3'), 7.67 (d, $J=2$ Hz, H-2') and 8.15 ($J=10$ Hz, H-4). This is the second report on the occurrence of knidilin in nature. Elution with benzene-chloroform (4 : 1) afforded xanthotoxin, m.p. 144° (yellow fluorescence in u.v, m.m.p., Co-TLC, IR and NMR).

The benzene-chloroform (1 : 1) eluate yielded a residue which on crystallization from petrol-ethyl acetate gave isopimpinellin, m.p. 148°-149°, pale yellow needles (brown fluorescence in u. v., m.m.p., Co-TLC, IR and NMR).

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Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of Some Halogeno-Chalcones and Flavones

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A number of chalcones and flavones have been shown active against various bacterial infections. Misra¹⁻³ have reported the germicidal activity of naphthyl and phenanthryl chalcones. Sharma et al.⁴

has reported the bactericidal activity of some flavones. Therefore an attempt was made to study the antimicrobial activity of some chalcones and flavones, synthesised by halogenation of 2',4'-dihydroxyphenyl-2 : 3-benzostyryl ketone.

On keeping resacetophenone and α -naphthaldehyde in the presence of ethanolic potassium hydroxide for 16 hr. and then on acidification with concentrated hydrochloric acid gave a yellow product, which gave violet red coloration with ferric chloride and yellow coloration to Wilson test⁵. Yellow product on methylation and acetylation gave dimethoxy and diacetyl chalcone respectively. Further infrared spectra of compound showed a band at 1625 cm^{-1} due to carbonyl group and band at 1540 cm^{-1} due to carbon carbon double bond. Therefore 2',4'-dihydroxyphenyl-2 : 3-benzostyryl ketone structure was assigned to it.

2',4'-dihydroxyphenyl-2 : 3-benzostyryl ketone on iodination with one mole of iodine and iodic acid, gave monoiododerivative methyl ether of which on ethanolic potassium hydroxide hydrolysis gave the known α -naphthoic acid⁶. The monoiododerivative was also obtained by condensing 5-iodoresacetophenone⁷, with α -naphthaldehyde in presence of ethanolic potassium hydroxide. Therefore 2',4'-dihydroxyphenyl-5'-iodo-2 : 3-benzostyryl ketone structure was assigned to the above monoiododerivative. With two, three or with eight moles of iodinating agent, it gave a di-iododerivative. Methylene ether of which on hydrolysis with ethanolic potassium hydroxide hydrolysis gave a known α -naphthoic acid⁶. The di-iododerivative was also obtained by condensing 3,5-di-iodoresacetophenone⁷, with α -naphthaldehyde in presence of ethanolic potassium hydroxide. 2',4'-dihydroxy-3',5'-di-iodophenyl-2 : 3-benzostyryl ketone structure was therefore assigned to the above di-iododerivative.

With one or two moles of bromine in acetic acid, 2',4'-dihydroxyphenyl-2 : 3-benzostyryl ketone did not give any pure product but with excess of bromine in acetic acid (eight moles), yielded a tetrabromoderivative. Methylene ether of which on ethanolic alkaline hydrolysis gave a known 3,5-dibromo-4-methoxy salicylic acid⁸. Tetrabromoderivative on heating with acetic acid and potassium acetate yielded dibromoflavone. Methyl ether of which on ethanolic alkaline hydrolysis gave a known 3,5-dibromo-4-methoxy salicylic acid⁸. Therefore, 6,8-dibromo-7-hydroxy-2-(α -naphthyl) chromone structure was assigned to above dibromoflavone and 2',4'-dihydroxyphenyl-3',5'- α - β -tetrabromo- β -1-naphthylethyl ketone to tetrabromoderivative.

The purity of all the compounds was checked by T.L.C.

All above chalcones gave yellow coloration to Wilson test⁶.

The infrared absorption spectra of these compounds (Table 2) in Nujol mulls showed the conjugated carbon carbon double bond band at 1600-1540 cm^{-1} (1-7-and

9-10). Further carbonyl stretching frequency in the case of compounds (1-7 and 9-10) appears in the region 1650-1600 cm^{-1} . While in the case of compound 8, it was found shifted to higher wavelength 1690 cm^{-1} (due to absence of aliphatic double bond). These assignments are in agreement with those observed by Mahanty et al⁹, in case of chalcones and Shaw and Simpson¹⁰ in flavones.

Antibacterial activity: All these compounds were tested for their antibacterial activity following the disc diffusion method¹¹, employing two organisms *Escherichia coli* and *Xanthomonas malvacearum*. Paper discs were dipped into the solutions of different compounds (100-150 ppm. of substance in 10% ethyl alcohol) and placed at the centres of the bacteria seeded agar plates. The discs were incubated at $30^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$ for 24 hr. The strength is reported by measuring the diameter of zone of inhibition in mm (Table 2) and results were standardised against chloromycetin, a commonly used antibiotic for *E. coli* and Agrimycin-100, a commonly employed in plant protection.

Experimental

2',4'-Dihydroxyphenyl-2:3-benzostyryl ketone. α -naphthaldehyde (10 g), resacetophenone (10 g.) were dissolved in ethyl alcohol (50 ml.) and potassium hydroxide solution (10%, 20 ml.) added to it. Reaction mixture was kept in bulb oven at 60° for 16 hr. and then diluted with ice cold water. Reaction mixture on acidification with conc. hydrochloric acid, gave a yellow product. The compound melting point and analytical data are given in Table 1.

2',4'-Diacetoxyphenyl-2:3-benzostyryl ketone: Above chalcone (0.5 g), acetic anhydride (2 ml.) and few drops of pyridine were taken in a flask and kept for 6 hr. Reaction mixture was then diluted with cold water, when the product separated. It crystallised from acetic acid (25%) in pale yellow needles. The melting point and analytical data are given in Table 1.

TABLE 2—INFRARED ABSORPTION DATA AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY OF CHALCONES AND FLAVONES.

Compound Nos as in Table 1	Frequency cm^{-1} >C=O	Frequency cm^{-1} >C=C<	Diameter of zone of inhibition (mm) <i>E. coli</i> , <i>X. malvacearum</i>
1	1625	1540	9
2	1630	1600	Nil
3	—	—	6
4	1600	1545	11
5	1645	1590	Nil
6	1610	1575	24
7	1650	1580	Nil
8	1690	—	9
9	1642	1595	20
10	1625	1570	16
Agrimycin-100	—	—	—
Chloromycetin	—	—	48

Iodination, bromination and methylation: Iodination, bromination and methylation of the compounds were carried as described earlier⁸. Melting points and analytical data are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compound No.	Compounds	M. P.* $^{\circ}\text{C}$	Crystal appearance	Molecular formula	Analysis %	
					Found	Required
1	2',4'-Dihydroxyphenyl-2:3-benzostyryl ketone	210	Yellow powdery crystals ^b	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5$	C, 78.65 H, 4.98	C, 78.62 H, 4.82
2	2',4'-Dimethoxyphenyl-2:3-benzostyryl ketone	116	Pale yellow prisms ^e	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_5$	C, 79.07 H, 5.20	C, 79.24 H, 5.66
3	2',4'-Diacetoxyphenyl-2:3-benzostyryl ketone	112	Pale yellow needles ^e	$\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_5$	C, 73.24 H, 4.91	C, 73.79 H, 4.81
4	2',4'-Dihydroxy-5-iodophenyl-2:3-benzostyryl ketone	211	Orange needles ^t	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_5\text{I}$	I, 30.38	I, 30.52
5	5'-iodo-2',4'-dimethoxyphenyl-2:3-benzostyryl ketone	141	Pale yellow prisms ^e	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_5\text{I}$	C, 57.11 H, 4.10 I, 28.50	C, 56.76 H, 3.83 I, 28.60
6	2',4'-Dihydroxy-3',5'-di-iodophenyl-2:3-benzostyryl ketone	181	Yellow prisms ^b	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_5\text{I}_2$	I, 46.96	I, 46.86
7	3',5'-Di-iodo-2',4'-di-methoxyphenyl-2:3-benzostyryl ketone	145	Yellow prisms ^e	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_5\text{I}_2$	C, 44.40 H, 2.92 I, 44.05	C, 44.21 H, 2.80 I, 44.50
8	2',4'-dihydroxyphenyl-3',5'- β -tetra-bromo- β -naphthylethyl ketone	212	Yellow needles ^t	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_5\text{Br}_4$	Br, 52.34	Br, 52.63
9	6,8-Dibromo-7-methoxy-2-(α -naphthyl) chromone	246	Yellow needles ^a	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_5\text{Br}_2$	C, 52.30 H, 2.96 Br, 34.48	C, 52.17 H, 2.60 Br, 34.78
10	6,8-Dibromo-7-hydroxy-2-(α -naphthyl) chromone	276	Pale pink needles ^a	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5\text{Br}_2$	C, 51.30 H, 2.71 Br, 36.12	C, 51.11 H, 2.24 Br, 35.87

*All melting points are uncorrected. Crystallised from: t=toluene; a=acetic acid; e=ethyl alcohol; b=benzene

